

Global funding for cancer research between 2016 and 2020: a content analysis of public and philanthropic investments.

Article Summary:

The text highlights the significant burden of cancer globally, with over 19.3 million cases and 10 million deaths in 2020, emphasizing the critical role of research in understanding, intervening, and improving outcomes for cancer patients. The study aimed to examine global trends in public and philanthropic funding for cancer research between 2016 and 2020, using data from the UberResearch Dimensions database and Cancer Research UK. It analyzed project and program grants, fellowships, and pilot projects while excluding funding for operational cancer care.

Key findings include:

1. Funding Overview:
 - a. A total of 66,388 funding awards were identified, amounting to approximately \$24.5 billion.
 - b. Funding declined each year, with a significant drop between 2019 and 2020.
2. Allocation by Research Phase:
 - a. Pre-clinical research dominated, receiving 73.5% of funding.
 - b. Phase 1–4 clinical trials received 7.4%, public health research 9.4%, and cross-disciplinary research 5.0%.
3. Cancer Types Funded:
 - a. The most funded cancers were breast cancer, hematological cancers, and brain cancer.
4. Cross-Cutting Themes:
 - a. Cancer biology research received the highest share (41.2%).
 - b. Drug treatment research accounted for 19.6%, and immuno-oncology for 12.1%.
 - c. Surgery research received only 1.4%, radiotherapy 2.8%, and global health studies a mere 0.5%.
5. Funding Disparities:
 - a. The majority of funding targets high-income countries, while low- and middle-income countries, which bear 80% of the cancer burden, receive limited support.

The authors stress the need to align funding with the global cancer burden and advocate for more equitable investment, especially in low-income and middle-income countries. They highlight the urgency of prioritizing research into surgery and radiotherapy, as these are crucial treatments for many solid tumors.

Table 1

Between January 1, 2016, and December 31, 2020, a total of \$24.5 billion was invested in cancer research, with the median award size (excluding Cancer Research UK) being \$90,576. The majority of funding (73.5%, or \$18 billion) went to pre-clinical research, covering 87.1% of all awards. Phase 1–4 clinical trials received 7.4% (\$1.8 billion) of the funding, while public health research accounted for 9.4% (\$2.3 billion). Cross-disciplinary research received 5.0% (\$1.2 billion).

In terms of cancer research focus, general cancer research received the largest share, \$7.1 billion (29.2%), more than twice the funding for any specific cancer type, such as breast cancer. Other highly funded cancer types included hematological, brain, lung, prostate, colorectal, pancreatic, and skin cancers. Research into multiple cancer types received \$2.1 billion (8.7%).

When analyzing research themes, cancer biology was the largest recipient with \$9.6 billion (41.2% of total funding), followed by drug treatment studies (\$4.6 billion, 19.6%). Diagnosis, screening, and monitoring research received \$3.0 billion (12.8%), immuno-oncology \$2.8 billion (12.1%), and survivorship and psychosocial research \$1.2 billion (5.0%). Radiotherapy and surgery received smaller shares, \$0.7 billion (2.8%) and \$0.3 billion (1.4%), respectively. Global health oncology studies received \$0.1 billion (0.5%), and research on metastatic disease totaled \$2.3 billion (9.8%).

This analysis excludes data from Cancer Research UK where detailed breakdowns were unavailable.

The USA provided \$14.0 billion (57.3%) of total cancer research funding, with the US National Institutes of Health being the largest individual funder. The UK and the European Commission were the next largest contributors. China and Japan, despite contributing 22.8% and 18.8% of awards respectively, had smaller median award sizes (\$58,086 for China and \$39,872 for Japan) compared to the US and UK, leading to their contributions being 4.4% and 4.1% of total global funding.

Figure

Global oncology research funding decreased annually from \$6.6 billion in 2016 (27% of total funding) to \$2.9 billion in 2020 (11.9%), coinciding with the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic. Despite the overall decline in funding, the distribution of funding across different research phases remained consistent throughout the five years.

Table 2

Cancer research funding was ranked by global disease burden across 18 cancer types using metrics like DALYs, YLD, and mortality. Brain cancer received the most research funding relative to its burden, ranking highest in all metrics, while lung cancer was the least funded, ranking lowest in DALYs, mortality, and 14th for YLD. Thyroid cancer ranked second-lowest overall and had the least funding per YLD.

In terms of investment per DALY, brain cancer received the highest funding (\$134.48), followed by breast cancer (\$122.40). The lowest funded were cholangiocarcinoma (\$9.57) and lung cancer (\$5.89). For investment per mortality, brain and breast cancers ranked highest, while hematological (\$170.70) and lung cancers (\$133.25) were the lowest. Brain and liver cancers received the highest funding per YLD, with testicular (\$168.91) and thyroid (\$109.39) cancers receiving the least.

Authors:

1. **Stuart A McIntosh** - Professor at Patrick G Johnston Center for Cancer Research at Queen's University Belfast. His research focuses on cancer, especially on their diagnosis and personalization of therapy. His scientific achievements testify to the impact of his work on international oncology. H-index - 30
2. **Fareeha Alam** - A researcher at the University College London. She focuses on interdisciplinary approaches to cancer research, including data analysis and clinical strategies. Her work contributes to developing more precise treatment methods.
3. **Laura Adams** - A doctor from Leeds Teaching Hospitals NHS Trust. Her research concerns the clinical aspects of cancer treatment, including the effectiveness of therapy in hospital conditions. H-index - 2
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5. **Jonathan Callaghan** - A young researcher from Queen's University Belfast, who is interested in genetic and molecular cancer mechanisms. H-index 2
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28. **Ramsey I Cutress** - Professor of Surgical Oncology at the University of Southampton. His work concerns personalized surgical treatment and modern cancer therapies. H-index 36
29. **Michael G Head** - Researcher from the University of Southampton. He focuses on analyzing global investments in medical research, including oncology, supporting the effectiveness of financing science. H-index 22

Journal:

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